

SINGAPORE DIGITAL PRESERVATION COMMUNITY OF INTEREST

TO FURTHER ADVOCACY AND ENGAGEMENT

First a Practitioner, Then a Leader

The National Library Singapore's digital preservation policy sets out our commitment to digitisation and digital preservation of Singapore's documentary heritage and **long-term strategic goal of being a leader in the field of digital preservation.**

In that vein, the National Library provides staff with opportunities to further **develop their skills with courses, seminars, conferences and self-directed learning,** ensuring all relevant **staff are appropriately skilled to carry out digital preservation activities.**

DPC's Robin Wright speaking on 15 May 2024

NLB joined the Digital Preservation Coalition (DPC) in 2021 to actively engage with the wider community and learn from other professional bodies, and has been **advocating digital preservation practices by engaging practitioners and the general public.**

Between 2021 and 2024, the National Library has organised **in-house talks** as well as actively **collaborated with DPC experts** to hold a workshop and talks, sharing knowledge on digital preservation topics and amassing a total of over 1,000 participants over the 4 years.

Deepening Collaboration with the New Singapore Community of Interest

From left: Speakers from NUS Libraries, Heritage Conservation Centre and National Library Board moderated by National Library Singapore

To bring engagement to the next level, the National Library Singapore spearheaded a new **digital preservation community of interest** amongst local tertiary libraries and heritage institutions with the objectives to:

1. Build a thriving local community that:

- Supports, encourages, and engages all members.
- Inspires active participation in digital preservation efforts.
- Encourages members to **reinvest their time in advancing preservation** within their own organisations.

2. Facilitate sharing between practitioners from different disciplines, enabling members to:

- Deepen collaboration through **networking.**
- Gain access to **shared experiences, resources, and tools.**

The inaugural session hosted a panel of speakers from **National University of Singapore Libraries, Heritage Conservation Centre and the National Library Board Singapore** who presented "The Digitisation Journey & Experience of NUS Libraries", "Preserving Time-Based Media Art in the National Collection", and "Digitisation and Digital Preservation Workflow" in the respective order.

It was followed by a **moderated Q&A** session that:

1. Fostered **multilateral engagement between members of the audience and the panel.**
2. Provided a **multidisciplinary exchange of insights and perspectives.**

Inaugural Session: Reception and Feedback

69 participants from a mix of government, heritage, and tertiary institutions participated in the session.

What did you find useful in this session?

"Hearing about how digital preservation is done for different fields, especially for time-based media and research data."

"Frank look at the difficulties of digital preservation and how considerations can cut across the different presenters."

"A stimulating discussion on the merits and limitations of cloud storage in the digital preservation space, as well as deeper insights into the specificities of time-based media preservation."

"The sharing by personnels from different organisations broaden my perspective on practices adopted by different organisations."

This session encouraged me to further develop my understanding and practice of digital preservation.

The session provided clarity and deepened my understanding of digital preservation.

Legend: Agree (orange), Strongly Agree (blue), Neither Agree nor Disagree (red)

I found this session:

The response was positive with clear interest indicated for other topics, showing **potential for future sessions.**

The success of the session can be attributed to the **open communication** between the speakers and audience through the moderated Q&A, encouraging candid sharing of **information outside of the panel's presentations** and opportunities to get **immediate answers from experts** present.

Impact survey

A follow-up survey was conducted in September to investigate the networking and learning impact of the session.

Respondents were encouraged to build connections with speakers and other participants, **30%** shared they were able to network with others during or after the event, and **50%** responded they intend to form connections in future sessions.

Average scores out of 5

Results show a healthy interest in topics such as digital preservation workflows, formats, metadata and systems.

80% like sessions with **moderated Q&A**, and **27%** have indicated interest in **being a speaker** for upcoming sessions.

With these results, the foreseeable longer-term impact of the community of interest include:

- **More collaboration** by engaging with peers from other institutions.
- **Improved trust** with increased transparency in practices, fostering a **culture of openness** where institutions feel safer to share methods, challenges, and ideas.
- **Lowered barriers to learning** with access to valuable expertise and insights, **raising the overall skill level and maturity of digital preservation efforts** in Singapore.